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**Non-cooperative game theory to ensure the marketability
of organic fertilizers within a sustainable circular economy**

Selene Cobo^{†,*}, Fengqi You[‡], Antonio Dominguez-Ramos[†] and Angel Irabien[†]

[†]Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, University of Cantabria
Avda. los Castros 46, Santander, 39005, Spain

[‡]Robert Frederick Smith School of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, Cornell
University, Ithaca, NY 14853, USA

*Corresponding author: Selene Cobo
E-mail: selencob@hotmail.com

16 **ABSTRACT**

17

18 To optimize the environmental performance and the conflicting economic interests of the
19 stakeholders that interact within circular integrated waste management systems (CIWMSs), life
20 cycle analysis and game theoretical models – based on the Stackelberg equilibrium – were
21 integrated into a multi-objective optimization framework. The framework was used to determine
22 the operational decisions and the configuration of a CIWMS that simultaneously minimize the total
23 global warming impacts (GWI) and maximize the profits of i) the waste managers that valorize the
24 municipal organic waste generated in the Spanish region of Cantabria, and ii) the regional farmers
25 that purchase the organic fertilizers derived from this waste. The resulting bilevel problem was
26 solved applying the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions. The balance between the stakeholders'
27 objectives is reflected in the low prices set for the organic fertilizers (0-2 €·metric ton⁻¹ of compost,
28 and 0-1 €·metric ton⁻¹ of digestate). Although the minimal GWI are constrained by the waste
29 managers' profits, it is possible to push the Pareto frontier toward better outcomes increasing the
30 waste management taxes. The proposed framework proved to be a useful instrument to plan for a
31 sustainable circular economy, warranting that the production and purchase of organic fertilizers is
32 profitable for both ends of the supply chain.

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34

35 **KEYWORDS**

36 Circular integrated waste management systems

37 Organic waste

38 Nutrient recovery

39 Stackelberg game

40 Multi-objective optimization

41 Life cycle assessment

42 Global warming impacts

43 Life Cycle Costing

44 INTRODUCTION

45

46 The economic sector that encompasses agriculture, forestry and other land uses emits almost a
47 quarter of the anthropogenic greenhouse gases.¹ The nitrogen use efficiency of the most cultivated
48 crops is typically below 40%; the remaining nitrogen is released to the atmosphere as N₂O – a
49 powerful greenhouse gas – or leaches into the water bodies causing eutrophication.² Moreover,
50 around 45% of the phosphorus mined worldwide for agricultural purposes ends in the ocean,
51 contributing to eutrophication and the depletion of this non-renewable nutrient.³

52

53 On the other hand, solid waste management accounts for about 5% of global warming impacts
54 (GWI).⁴ The diversion of organic waste from landfills prevents the degradation of carbon into CH₄ –
55 a significant contributor to global warming – that occurs under the anaerobic conditions of landfills,
56 and represents an opportunity for nutrient recovery; it has been estimated that the total nitrogen,
57 phosphorus and potassium contained in food, animal and human waste amount to 2.7 times the
58 nutrients processed by the fertilizer industry.⁵

59

60 Finding a common strategy to meet the ever-increasing demand for nutrients and manage organic
61 waste while minimizing the associated environmental impacts and the removal of resources from
62 the environment falls within the scope of a circular economic system. However, a standardized
63 systematic approach to quantify, assess and optimize the performance of a circular economy is still
64 lacking.

65

66 Cobo et al.^{6,7} illustrated how process systems engineering can effectively assist decision-makers in
67 this respect by developing a life cycle optimization framework for the sustainable design of Circular
68 Integrated Waste Management Systems (CIWMSs) targeting nutrient circularity. Nonetheless, their
69 study did not consider that an increase in the market share of the fertilizing products recovered
70 from organic waste (hereafter referred to as organic fertilizers) can only be achieved if farmers are
71 willing to purchase these products.

72

73 Indeed, the worse performance of organic fertilizers compared with industrial fertilizers – more
74 product is required to fertilize the same area –^{8,9} renders them uncompetitive in the absence of
75 subsidies. To avert a scenario where waste managers do not get back a return on the investment

76 made in sustainable technologies and accumulate a stock of organic fertilizers that cannot be sold,
77 trade-offs between their economic interests and those of the farmers must be made. Therefore,
78 modeling the farmers' response to the prices set for the organic fertilizers is critical to accurately
79 foresee the behavior of CIWMSs.

80

81 Game theory can be applied to optimize the decisions and actions of all the parties involved in a
82 circular supply chain in accordance with their individual – and conflicting – objectives. Nevertheless,
83 few studies have reportedly approached the design of circular systems from a game theoretical
84 perspective. Some authors have analyzed the payoff matrices derived from the alternative decisions
85 that the relevant actors within circular systems can make,¹⁰⁻¹³ whereas others have developed more
86 complex optimization frameworks.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ To the best of the authors' knowledge, the optimization of
87 the interactions between the waste managers that valorize municipal organic waste and the farmers
88 that purchase the resulting fertilizing products has not been described in the literature.

89

90 Thus, the goal of this paper is to explore how game theory optimization can be used to plan for the
91 implementation of a sustainable circular economy of nutrients by guaranteeing that the production
92 and agricultural application of organic fertilizers is profitable for both ends of the supply chain. This
93 research builds on previous studies that focus on a CIWMS aimed at the valorization of the municipal
94 organic waste generated in the Spanish region of Cantabria.⁷⁻⁹ The results of the study will determine
95 the operational decisions and the configuration of the Cantabrian CIWMS that minimize its GWI and
96 optimize the economic performance of the involved stakeholders. Specifically, the research will
97 reveal the types of organic fertilizers that must be produced and the range of prices that should be
98 assigned to them to ensure their acceptance in the market under the restrictions of the case study.

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100

101 **METHODOLOGY**

102

103 The integration of life cycle and game theoretical models underpinned the holistic and decentralized
104 optimization of the system. The assumptions made and the methodological procedure followed are
105 described below.

106 **System model**

107

108 Figure 1 depicts the superstructure containing all the alternative unit processes that could be
109 integrated into the optimal system design. Once the unit processes were separately characterized,
110 the system model was constructed in the GAMS (General Algebraic Modeling System) 28.2.0
111 optimization platform.¹⁷

112

113 To align this modular modeling approach with the game theoretical model that describes the
114 stakeholders' behavior, the unit processes were split into two subsystems comprising the activities
115 of different groups of agents: the waste management and the agricultural subsystems. The
116 boundaries that delimit the studied CIWMS and the two subsystems are identified in Figure 1.

117

118 Regarding the spatiotemporal boundaries of the study, the CIWMS processes the municipal organic
119 waste collected from all the Cantabrian municipalities in one year (83,544 metric ton).¹⁸ The
120 farmers, who purchase the amount of fertilizing products required to grow their crops during that
121 year, are located across the region.

122

123

124 - *Life cycle model*

125

126 An attributional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) model (based on average data and focusing on the
127 environmentally relevant flows that enter and exit the system)¹⁹ was developed. The functional unit
128 was defined as the area that must be annually fertilized to meet the nutrient requirements of the
129 two most cultivated crops in Cantabria – corn and wheat –, which in 2018 occupied 4,118 and 674
130 ha, respectively.²⁰ The analyzed CIWMS also supplies the electricity generated at the incineration,
131 landfill and anaerobic digestion unit processes. To address the system multi-functionality, the direct
132 substitution method was applied, presuming that the electricity generated by the CIWMS replaces
133 the same amount of electricity produced with the average Spanish technology mix.

134

135 The GWI were modeled with the ReCiPe 1.11 method,²¹ considering a 100-year time horizon. The
136 biogenic carbon derived from food waste was quantified as neutral; i.e., it was assumed to have
137 been removed from the atmosphere in the crop production stage.

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Figure 1. System boundaries and superstructure

158 The LCA of the individual unit processes that compose the system was carried out with the
159 EASETECH (Environmental Assessment System for Environmental Technologies) 2.3.6 software.²²
160 EASETECH also calculated the composition and flows of the streams exiting each unit process, which
161 served as the input data to the models of the units that further process those streams. The DNDC
162 (Denitrification-Decomposition) 9.5 simulation model²³ was used to predict the mean annual
163 fertilization requirements, crop yields, and carbon and nitrogen emissions due to the application of
164 the different fertilizers to the soil in the 100-year timeframe. The DNDC results were transferred to
165 EASETECH to determine the associated GWI. The data required to conduct the LCA, namely the
166 waste composition (Appendix A), the life cycle inventories of the waste management unit processes
167 (Appendix B), and the DNDC input data and results (Appendix C) are in the Supporting Information.

168

169 Life Cycle Costing was used to determine the stakeholders' profits. The economic models of the
170 waste management unit processes were mainly derived from SWOLF (Solid Waste Optimization
171 Lifecycle Framework),²⁴ whereas various sources provided the data to estimate the farmers'
172 profits.²⁵⁻³¹ The selected reference year for the economic data related to the waste management
173 and the agricultural subsystems (Appendix D) is 2015.

174

175 It was assumed that the waste managers are free to fix a gate price for the compost and digestate
176 between -10 and 10 €·metric ton⁻¹. It is not unusual for European waste managers to pay for the
177 transportation and spreading costs of the organic fertilizers,^{32,33} even negative prices have been
178 reported as a measure to incentivize farmers to purchase organic fertilizers.³⁴ The same minimum
179 gate prices were considered for the struvite and (NH₄)₂SO₄ produced by subjecting the liquid
180 digestate to struvite precipitation and ammonia stripping and absorption processes, but their
181 maximum gate prices were calculated as the product of their nitrogen and phosphorus content and
182 the market values of the industrially synthesized (NH₄)₂SO₄³⁵ and (NH₄)₂HPO₄,³⁶ expressed per kg of
183 nitrogen and phosphorus, respectively.

184

185 The capital costs of the unit processes available in the current Cantabrian waste management plant
186 (differentiated in Figure 1 with a discontinuous line) and the costs associated with the farmers'
187 equipment and land were assumed to be already amortized. The capital costs of the other unit
188 processes were annualized considering an amortization period of 15 years and a 7% interest rate,
189 consistently with the Spanish banks' lending rates.³⁷

190

191 A previous study suggested that the GWI related to infrastructure do not constitute a significant
192 fraction of the total GWI of waste management systems,³⁸ and therefore the GWI of the capital
193 goods were excluded from the analysis.

194

195 Another weakness of the model is that DNDC considers that all the phosphorus contained in the
196 organic fertilizers is in a mineral form that the crops can easily take up. Although this is a common
197 supposition,³⁹ certain studies pinpoint that the products recovered from municipal organic waste
198 contain small amounts of organic phosphorus.⁴⁰⁻⁴²

199

200

201 - *Game theoretical model*

202

203 The Stackelberg game is a sequential game model that makes a distinction between two types of
204 non-cooperative players – the leader and the followers – who do not coordinate their strategies and
205 only seek to optimize their own performance. The leader has the strategic advantage of making the
206 initial decisions knowing how the followers will respond.⁴³ The Stackelberg game reflects the
207 hierarchical relationships between leaders and followers, and thus it was applied to model the case
208 study; the waste managers were identified as the leaders, who determine the quantities and prices
209 of the produced organic fertilizers, and the farmers, as the followers who decide which product to
210 purchase among the fertilizers available in the market. The waste managers must anticipate that,
211 given the choice between alternative fertilizing products that provide the same function, the
212 farmers will acquire the ones with the lowest associated costs.

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214

215 **Optimization method**

216

217 The Stackelberg game was formulated as a bilevel optimization problem, in which the upper level
218 problem corresponds to the leader's problem, and the nested lower level problem, to the followers'
219 problem.⁴⁴ To solve the bilevel problem, it was reformulated into a single-level problem by means
220 of the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions, which – provided that the lower level problem is convex –
221 transform the lower level problem into a set of constraints appended to the upper level problem.⁴⁵

222 If the problem included discrete lower level variables, a more complex reformulation algorithm
223 would be required.^{46,47} Reformulating the bilevel problem allows the upper and lower level
224 problems to be solved concurrently to attain a Nash equilibrium where none of the players can
225 improve their performance by unilaterally changing their actions; i.e., each player adopts the
226 strategies that optimize their objectives given the actions taken by the other players.⁴³

227

228 Although the minimization of the GWI of the entire system entails decisions in the upper and lower
229 level problems, given the limited information that the followers have access to, and their more
230 restricted decision-making power, the environmental objective function was considered as one of
231 the leader's goals.⁴⁸ To simultaneously optimize the leader's environmental and economic
232 objectives, a multi-objective optimization approach was adopted. Following the ϵ -constraint
233 method,⁴⁹ a set of Pareto-efficient solutions – all of which are better than the others in at least one
234 criterion – was obtained.

235

236

237 **PROBLEM STATEMENT**

238

239 The reformulated single level problem – a single period mixed integer linear program composed of
240 345,234 constraints, 148,470 continuous variables and 1,597 binary variables – was solved with the
241 CPLEX algorithm⁵⁰ in an Intel^(R) Core^(TM) i7 CPU-4500U of 1.8 GHz and 8 GB of RAM. Setting the
242 absolute optimality tolerance to 0, the computational time varied between 40 minutes and 27
243 hours, depending on the selected scenario and the defined constraints.

244

245

246 **Upper level problem**

247

248 The leader's profits were calculated as the sum of the annual revenues from the sale of organic
249 fertilizers and the waste management tax paid by the municipalities minus the Total Annual Costs
250 (TAC) of the waste management subsystem. To maximize the waste managers' profits and minimize
251 the total GWI of the CIWMS, the leaders must make decisions on the configuration of the waste
252 management subsystem and the price of the organic fertilizers.

253

254 The optimal design of the waste management subsystem is determined by the binary variables that
255 indicate which unit processes integrate this subsystem and the continuous variables that reflect the
256 amount of waste that each unit process handles. As Figure 1 illustrates, only the municipal organic
257 waste that has been source separated is allowed into the solid waste recycling processes (wet
258 thermophilic anaerobic digestion and tunnel or windrow composting); the organic waste that has
259 been mixed with inorganic materials must be sent to the landfill or the grate incinerator, along with
260 the solid rejects of the other unit processes. Hence, the Source Separation Rate (SSR) – the fraction
261 of municipal organic waste that is source separated – was identified as one of the leader’s decision
262 variables.

263

264 The price of the organic fertilizers was defined as an upper level decision variable that equates the
265 sum of the product of a matrix of binary variables ($y_{p,r}$) and a matrix of parameters within the
266 predefined range of gate prices ($FP_{p,r}$). This formulation allowed us to apply Glover’s method⁵¹ to
267 linearize the product of a continuous and a binary variable, ensuring that the solutions to the
268 optimization problem are global optimums.

269

270 The system model relies on the assumption that all the produced organic fertilizers are sold to the
271 regional farmers. This equation limits the amount of produced organic fertilizers (upper level
272 variable) to the total amount of organic fertilizers purchased by the farmers (lower level variable),
273 which is in turn restricted by the fertilization requirements of the regionally grown corn and wheat,
274 quantified in the lower level problem. Nevertheless, the mass balance that connects the waste
275 management and agricultural subsystems constitutes an upper level constraint because the waste
276 managers are the stakeholders in control of the production and sale operations. In addition to the
277 mass and energy balances that describe the waste management subsystem, the upper level problem
278 must satisfy these constraints:

- 279 • The waste managers’ profits must be positive.
- 280 • Different types of composting processes cannot be concurrently integrated into the system.
- 281 • Capacity restrictions. The minimal and maximal capacity restrictions of the waste management
282 unit processes are shown in Table S47 of the Supporting Information. The minimal capacity
283 restrictions were set as a requisite for the construction of new infrastructure to avoid the
284 nonlinearities derived from the exponential equations that quantify how the TAC of the waste
285 management unit processes decrease as the annual waste flows that they handle increase.⁵²⁻⁵⁷

286 These restrictions enabled us to assume that the incremental changes in the TAC with the
287 incoming waste flows are constant. The validity of this assumption was investigated in Figures
288 S10-S19, which compare the TAC considered in this study with the TAC exponential curves
289 provided in the literature.^{55,57}

- 290 • New waste management unit processes with the same function as those already present in the
291 Cantabrian waste management plant can only be implemented if the capacities of the previous
292 ones are exceeded.
- 293 • In accordance with Directive 1999/31/EC,⁵⁸ the amount of landfilled biodegradable waste is
294 limited to 35% of the total biodegradable municipal solid waste produced in 1995.

295

296

297 **Lower level problem**

298

299 The followers, who aim at maximizing their annual profits by reacting rationally to the leader's
300 decisions, are the regional farmers that cultivate corn and wheat. Each farmer is characterized by
301 their geographic location, the type of cereal they grow and the area they have available for crop
302 production. A total of 63 followers were identified, only three of whom harvest wheat. Appendix E
303 compiles the data that describe the farmers' activities, including the road distances from the
304 agricultural sites to the waste management plant and to the two closest fertilizer plants, which are
305 assumed to supply all the industrial fertilizers.

306

307 The amount and type of fertilizers purchased by each farmer depend on the chosen fertilization
308 strategy. To account for the fact that the nitrogen/phosphorus ratio in the organic fertilizers
309 (excluding $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$) is lower than the proportion of these nutrients required by corn and wheat,
310 three fertilization strategies were defined:

- 311 1. Application of industrial fertilizers (NH_4NO_3 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$) to satisfy the crop demand for
312 nitrogen and phosphorus. Farmers acquire these products from the nearest fertilizer plant to
313 their fields.
- 314 2. Application of organic fertilizers to cover the crop nitrogen requirements. This strategy leads to
315 excess phosphorus in the soil, unless $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ is applied, in which case $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ must be
316 added.

317 3. Application of organic fertilizers to supply the phosphorus needed by the crop. To correct the
 318 nitrogen deficiency, NH_4NO_3 is provided.

319

320 The followers' decisions are reflected by variable $xf_{c,m,p,s}$, which was defined as the amount of each
 321 type of fertilizer purchased by each farmer and applied to the soil in accordance with each
 322 fertilization strategy. The other variables and parameters involved in the lower level problem are
 323 described in the nomenclature section.

324

325 The lower level problem was formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \max z(xf_{c,m,p,s}, y_{p,r}) \equiv & \sum_{c \in C} \sum_{m \in M} \sum_{p \in P} \sum_{s \in S} \frac{CP_c \cdot Yield_{c,p,s}}{P_{c,p,s}} \cdot xf_{c,m,p,s} & (1) \\ & - \left(\sum_{r \in R} FP_{p,r} \cdot y_{p,r} + IFP_{c,p} + sc + tc \cdot Dp_m \right) \cdot O_{c,m,p,s} \cdot xf_{c,m,p,s} \\ & - \left(\frac{\sum_{f \in F} CF_{c,f,p,s} \cdot (CFP_f + sc + tc \cdot Df_m) \cdot O_{c,m,p,s}}{P_{c,p,s}} \right) \cdot xf_{c,m,p,s} - (wc \cdot w_c + lc) \cdot At_{c,m} \end{aligned}$$

$$s. t. h_1(xf_{c,m,p,s}, Aorg_{c,m}) \equiv Aorg_{c,m} - \sum_{p \in P} \sum_{s \in S} \frac{xf_{c,m,p,s}}{P_{c,p,s}} \cdot Vorg_p = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} h_2(xf_{c,m,p,s}, Aorg_{c,m}) \equiv & \\ \sum_{p \in P} \sum_{s \in S} xf_{c,m,p,s} \cdot Vfert_{s,p} - & \left(\sum_{p \in P} \sum_{s \in S} P_{c,p,s} \cdot Vfert_{s,p} \right) \cdot (At_{c,m} - Aorg_{c,m}) = 0 & (3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} g_1(xf_{c,m,p,s}, y_{p,r}, Aorg_{c,m}) \equiv & \\ \sum_{p \in P} \sum_{s \in S} Vorg_p \cdot & \left(\sum_{r \in R} FP_{p,r} \cdot G_{r,c,m,p,s} + sc \cdot xf_{c,m,p,s} + tc \cdot Dp_m \cdot xf_{c,m,p,s} \right) \\ + Vorg_p \cdot & \frac{\sum_{f \in F} CF_{c,f,p,s} \cdot (CFP_f + sc + tc \cdot Df_m) \cdot O_{c,m,p,s}}{P_{c,p,s}} \cdot xf_{c,m,p,s} \\ - Aorg_{c,m} \cdot & \left(\sum_{p \in P} \sum_{s \in S} P_{c,p,s} \cdot Vind_p \cdot O_{c,m,p,s} \cdot (IFP_{c,p} + sc + tc \cdot Df_m) \right) \leq 0 \quad \forall c, m & (4) \end{aligned}$$

$$g_2(Aorg_{c,m}) \equiv Aorg_{c,m} - At_{c,m} \leq 0 \quad \forall c, m \quad (5)$$

$$g_3(xf_{c,m,p,s}) \equiv xf_{c,m,p,s} - At_{c,m} \cdot P_{c,p,s} \leq 0 \quad \forall c, m, p, s \quad (6)$$

$$g_4(xf_{c,m,p,s}) \equiv -xf_{c,m,p,s} \leq 0 \quad \forall c, m, p, s \quad (7)$$

326

327 The objective function was calculated as the annual revenues from the sale of grain minus the
 328 annual costs associated with fertilization (including the transportation and spreading of fertilizers),
 329 irrigation and labor.

330

331 Constraints h_1 and h_2 express that the total surface fertilized by the farmers must equal the area of
 332 their respective fields. Constraint g_1 captures the behavior of the followers in the Stackelberg game:
 333 if the cost of purchasing, transporting and spreading a given amount of organic fertilizers exceeds
 334 the cost of fertilizing the equivalent area with industrial fertilizers, the farmers will fertilize their
 335 fields solely with industrial fertilizers. Finally, constraints g_2 to g_4 indicate the upper and lower
 336 bounds of the lower level variables.

337

338

339 - *Reformulation of the lower level problem*

340

341 The leaders make their decisions prior to the followers, which allows the binary upper level variables
 342 that appear in the lower level problem ($y_{p,r}$) to be treated as parameters.^{43,45} In the absence of
 343 discrete variables, the lower level problem can be replaced by its Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions,
 344 which are composed of:

- 345 • Primal feasibility constraints. These are the lower level constraints: h_1, h_2, g_1, g_2, g_3 and g_4 .
- 346 • Dual feasibility constraints. They are based on the derivatives of the lower level functions with
 347 respect to the lower level variables:

$$\frac{(CP_c \cdot Yield_{c,p,s} - \sum_{f \in F} CF_{c,f,p,s} \cdot (CFP_f + sc + tc \cdot Df_m) + vor g_p \cdot \mu_{1_{c,m}}) \cdot O_{c,m,p,s}}{P_{c,p,s}} \quad (8)$$

$$- \left(\sum_{r \in R} FP_{p,r} \cdot y_{p,r} + IFP_{c,p} + sc + tc \cdot Dp_m - vfert_{s,p} \cdot \mu_{2_{c,m}} \right) \cdot O_{c,m,p,s}$$

$$- \left(\left(\sum_{r \in R} FP_{p,r} \cdot y_{p,r} + sc + tc \cdot Dp_m \right) + \frac{\sum_{f \in F} CF_{c,f,p,s} \cdot (CFP_f + sc + tc \cdot Df_m)}{P_{c,p,s}} \right) \cdot O_{c,m,p,s} \cdot Vor g_p \cdot \lambda_{1_{c,m}}$$

$$- \lambda_{3_{c,m,p,s}} \leq 0$$

$$\mu_{1_{c,m}} + \sum_{p \in P} \sum_{s \in S} P_{c,p,s} \cdot Vfert_{s,p} \cdot \mu_{2_{c,m}} \quad (9)$$

$$- \sum_{p \in P} \sum_{s \in S} P_{c,p,s} \cdot Vind_p \cdot O_{c,m,p,s} \cdot (IFP_{c,p} + sc + tc \cdot Df_m) \cdot \lambda_{1_{c,m}} + \lambda_{2_{c,m}} = 0$$

348

349 The domains of the auxiliary variables used to formulate the dual feasibility constraints are
 350 defined below:

351 $\mu_{1_{c,m}} \in \mathbb{R}$

352 $\mu_{2_{c,m}} \in \mathbb{R}$

$$\lambda_{1_{c,m}} \geq 0 \quad \forall c, m \tag{10}$$

$$\lambda_{2_{c,m}} \geq 0 \quad \forall c, m \tag{11}$$

$$\lambda_{3_{c,m,p,s}} \geq 0 \quad \forall c, m, p, s \tag{12}$$

353

354 • Complementary slackness constraints. They indicate that the product of the left-hand side of
 355 the inequalities that compose the lower level problem and their associated dual variables must
 356 equal 0:

$$\lambda_{1_{c,m}} \cdot \text{lhs}g_{1_{c,m}} = 0 \tag{13}$$

$$\lambda_{2_{c,m}} \cdot \text{lhs}g_{2_{c,m}} = 0 \tag{14}$$

$$\lambda_{3_{c,m,p,s}} \cdot \text{lhs}g_{3_{c,m,p,s}} = 0 \tag{15}$$

$$\text{lhs}dfcx_{c,m,p,s} \cdot \text{xf}_{c,m,p,s} = 0 \tag{16}$$

357

358 Each complementary nonlinear slackness constraint was replaced by two equivalent linear
 359 constraints using binary variables and a sufficiently large (or big-M) parameter:

$$\lambda_{1_{c,m}} \leq y_{1_{c,m}} \cdot M_{c,m} \quad \forall c, m \tag{17}$$

$$-\text{lhs}g_{1_{c,m}} \leq (1 - y_{1_{c,m}}) \cdot M_{c,m} \quad \forall c, m \tag{18}$$

$$\lambda_{2_{c,m}} \leq y_{2_{c,m}} \cdot M_{c,m} \quad \forall c, m \tag{19}$$

$$-\text{lhs}g_{2_{c,m}} \leq (1 - y_{2_{c,m}}) \cdot M_{c,m} \quad \forall c, m \tag{20}$$

$$\lambda_{3_{c,m,p,s}} \leq y_{3_{c,m,p,s}} \cdot M_{c,m,p,s} \quad \forall c, m, p, s \tag{21}$$

$$-\text{lhs}g_{3_{c,m,p,s}} \leq (1 - y_{3_{c,m,p,s}}) \cdot M_{c,m,p,s} \quad \forall c, m, p, s \tag{22}$$

$$\text{xf}_{c,m,p,s} \leq y_{4_{c,m,p,s}} \cdot M_{c,m,p,s} \quad \forall c, m, p, s \tag{23}$$

$$-\text{lhs}dfcx_{c,m,p,s} \leq (1 - y_{4_{c,m,p,s}}) \cdot M_{c,m,p,s} \quad \forall c, m, p, s \tag{24}$$

360

361 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

362

363 Before proceeding with the multi-objective optimization, the objective functions of the
364 reformulated single-level problem were separately optimized. The maximal profits that the waste
365 managers can earn, and the resulting GWI are represented in Figures 2A and 2C, whereas the profits
366 they would make if their only objective was to attain the minimal GWI (shown in Figure 2D) are
367 displayed in Figure 2B. In order to ascertain the influence of the uncertainty associated with the
368 behavior of the citizens responsible for waste generation and separation on the results, the single
369 objective optimization problems were solved for five SSR intervals ($0 \leq SSR \leq 0.1$, $0.1 \leq SSR \leq 0.2$,
370 $0.2 \leq SSR \leq 0.3$, $0.3 \leq SSR \leq 0.4$, $0.4 \leq SSR \leq 0.5$); i.e., an optimal SSR was obtained for each interval.

371

372 Figures 2A and 2B prove that, regardless of the SSR, the revenues derived from the sale of organic
373 fertilizers are negligible with respect to the waste management tax. Moreover, the costs related to
374 the collection and recycling of the source separated waste increase with the SSR, but the
375 incineration and landfilling costs are reduced.

376

377 The trade-off between the GWI of the waste management and agricultural subsystems is evidenced
378 in Figures 2C and 2D. In general, as the SSR increases, the agricultural subsystem is responsible for
379 more GWI because of the greater emissions associated with the transportation, spreading and soil
380 application of the larger mass of organic fertilizers required to fulfill the fertilization needs compared
381 with industrial fertilizers. Nonetheless, the GWI of the waste management subsystem decrease with
382 the SSR because more waste can be processed by the anaerobic digestion and composting
383 technologies instead of incinerated or landfilled

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385 Thus, as Figures 2A and 2D illustrate, the relationship between the SSRs and the optimal economic
386 and environmental objectives could be described with a curve; the optimal profits and GWI are
387 attained with the median SSR (0.25). However, that does not imply that the economic and
388 environmental objectives follow the same trend. Figure 2B shows that the waste managers' profits
389 would drop to nearly 0 if they only pursued a reduction in the GWI. These results provide grounds
390 for the multi-objective optimization.

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Figure 2. Results of the single-objective optimizations of the leader's objective functions in the reformulated single-level problem for the defined SSR intervals

394 Figure 3A depicts the Pareto fronts and the prices of the organic fertilizers obtained for two
395 scenarios: i) the decentralized scenario described by the bilevel problem, and ii) a centralized
396 scenario wherein the farmers' economic interests are disregarded. The latter was optimized solving
397 the upper level problem subject to the restrictions of the lower level problem. Both Pareto fronts
398 confirm that the optimal SSR range is 0.2-0.3, and that the improvement in the GWI is accomplished
399 at the expense of the waste managers' profits. The amount of digestate produced is progressively
400 reduced as the restriction on the GWI is relaxed, allowing the waste managers to increase their
401 profits.

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403 The balance between the farmers' and waste managers' economic interests in the decentralized
404 scenario is reflected in the lower prices set for the organic fertilizers (0-2 €·metric ton⁻¹ of compost,
405 and 0-1 €·metric ton⁻¹ of digestate), whereas in the centralized scenario the waste managers set the
406 maximum prices allowed by the restrictions of the lower level problem. The results of the
407 decentralized scenario are more consistent with the symbolic prices that European farmers usually
408 pay for organic fertilizers.³²⁻³⁴ The digestate is assigned lower prices than compost to compensate
409 for the larger mass of digestate required to achieve the same fertilizing function, and therefore the
410 digestate transportation and spreading costs are higher than those of compost.

411

412 The farmers' better economic performance in the decentralized scenario is accompanied by a
413 reduction in the waste managers' profits and increased GWI with respect to the centralized scenario.
414 This happens because the solutions to the bilevel problem rely to a greater extent on the use of the
415 organic fertilizers to cover the crops' phosphorus requirements, which reduces the amount of
416 (NH₄)₂HPO₄ needed. This fertilization strategy is based on the application of NH₄NO₃, a fertilizer that
417 is less expensive than (NH₄)₂HPO₄, but also has a higher carbon footprint. Nevertheless, as Figure 3A
418 shows, the relative differences between the leader's economic and environmental objectives in
419 both scenarios are not remarkable. This can be attributed to the small fraction of the revenues due
420 to the sale of organic fertilizers, and to the low contribution of the agricultural subsystem to the
421 overall GWI.

Figure 3. Pareto fronts and prices of the organic fertilizers for the analyzed scenarios

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Figures 2 and 3A show that the waste managers' margin for profits and environmental improvement are quite slight. However, the decision-makers can push the Pareto frontier changing some of the fixed operating decisions that act as model parameters. Since the waste management tax is the main source of income to the waste managers and hence it will determine the feasibility of the CIWMS, a sensitivity analysis considering increases of 25% and 50% in the current waste management tax was carried out for the decentralized scenario. The resulting Pareto fronts are presented in Figure 3B.

432 Raising the waste management tax could bring about reductions of up to 19% in the GWI, which are
433 significant compared with the maximal 11% reduction that can be achieved with the current tax.
434 The reason is that the minimal GWI are no longer limited by the restriction on the minimal profits
435 that the waste managers must make. The rise in the revenues allows the waste managers to
436 implement larger SSRs; the scenarios with the increased waste management taxes attain the
437 minimal GWI based on a 49% SSR, the valorization of all the source separated organic waste in the
438 anaerobic digester, and the ammonia stripping and absorption of the liquid digestate, which enables
439 the sale of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ for prices between 29 and 43 €-metric ton⁻¹. However, the optimal SSR the
440 waste managers should implement to maximize their profits irrespective of the tax is 25%.

441

442 The results of Figure 4 – which indicates the geographic location of the regional farmers and the
443 type of organic fertilizers they purchase –correspond to the Pareto optimal solutions that generate
444 54×10^6 kg CO₂-eq·year⁻¹ in the decentralized scenario. For all the analyzed waste management taxes,
445 the farmers that purchase the organic fertilizers are located within a 32 km radius around the waste
446 management plant; the farmers located further away opt to purchase industrial fertilizers to reduce
447 the transportation costs. In the scenario with the highest waste management tax, struvite is
448 produced at a price of 58.49 €-metric ton⁻¹. Struvite is the fertilizer sent to the farthest agricultural
449 site because of the lower amount of product required to fertilize the same area relative to the other
450 organic fertilizers.

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452 The individualized recommendations that can be made to the farmers and the waste managers
453 based on these results prove that the integration of life cycle and game theoretical models
454 constitutes an improvement with respect to the existing centralized life cycle optimization
455 frameworks.

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Figure 4. Distribution of organic fertilizers between the Cantabrian farmers for the Pareto solutions that generate 54×10^6 kg CO₂-eq·year⁻¹ in the decentralized scenarios with increased taxes. The size of the blank circles is proportional to the area of the field, and the size of the colored circles is proportional to the area fertilized with the organic fertilizers

476 **CONCLUSIONS**

477

478 The proposed optimization framework allows the analysis of the environmental and economic
479 consequences of the adoption of a circular economy through the lens of all the stakeholders, and
480 the simultaneous optimization of their decisions in accordance with their conflicting objectives.

481

482 The results demonstrate that a deviation from the objective of economic growth – understood as
483 an increase in profits – is needed to achieve a reduction in the GWI. To improve the competitiveness
484 of the organic fertilizers in the market, their prices must be set quite low with respect to the
485 industrially produced fertilizers. Therefore, the sale of organic fertilizers constitutes an insignificant
486 source of revenues for the waste managers; without economic incentives that spur the investment
487 in novel technologies, it is unlikely that waste managers will change their mindset and start viewing
488 organic wastes as valuable products.

489

490 Moreover, an 11% reduction in the GWI of the system can be achieved at most with the current
491 waste management tax, which suggests that the implementation of a circular economy is not the
492 most effective strategy to combat climate change.

493

494 Although these results cannot be extrapolated to other case studies, the developed framework can
495 be adapted to different systems. Future studies should model the behavior of the agents that
496 generate waste, who determine the amount of waste that is source separated and will be affected
497 by the changes in the waste management tax and the cost of staples.

498

499 The further improvements and deployment of this framework could bridge the gap between the
500 theoretical concept of a circular economy and its industrial applications, helping policy-makers
501 devise a roadmap to attain a sustainable circular economy.

502 **ABBREVIATIONS**

503

CIWMS	Circular Integrated Waste Management System
GW	Global Warming Impacts
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
SSR	Source Separation Rate
TAC	Total Annual Costs

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506 **NOMENCLATURE**

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508 **Sets**

509 *C* crops

510 *F* Industrial fertilizers

511 *M* Municipalities

512 *P* Fertilizers

513 *R* Prices of the organic fertilizers

514 *S* Fertilization strategies

515

516 **Upper level variable**

517 $y_{p,r}$ Binary decision on the price of the organic fertilizers

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519 **Lower level variables**

520 $A_{org_{c,m,p,s}}$ Area fertilized with the organic fertilizers (ha)

521 $TFC_{c,m,p,s}$ Total costs related to the purchase, transportation and spreading of the fertilizers (€·ha⁻¹)

522 $x_{f_{c,m,p,s}}$ Amount of each fertilizing product purchased by each follower and applied to the soil in
523 accordance with each fertilization strategy (kg)

524

525 **Reformulation variables**

526 $\mu_{1c,m}, \mu_{2c,m}, \lambda_{1c,m}, \lambda_{2c,m}, \lambda_{3c,m,p,s}$ Continuous variable used to define the dual feasibility constraints

- 527 $G_{r,c,m,p,s}$ Auxiliary variable used to apply Glover's linearization method and equal to the product of
528 $x_{f,c,m,p,s}$ and $y_{p,r}$
- 529 $lhsdfc_{c,m,p,s}$ Left-hand side of the dual feasibility constraint based on the derivatives with respect to
530 $x_{f,c,m,p,s}$
- 531 $lhsg1_{c,m}, lhsg2_{c,m}, lhsg3_{c,m,p,s}$ Left-hand side of constraints g1-g3
- 532 $Y1_{c,m}, Y2_{c,m}, Y3_{c,m,p,s}, Y4_{c,m,p,s}$ Binary variables used for the linearization of the complementary
533 slackness constraints
- 534
- 535 **Parameters**
- 536 $At_{c,m}$ Total fertilized area (ha)
- 537 $CF_{c,f,p,s}$ Amount of industrial fertilizers required to complement the fertilization of 1 ha with organic
538 fertilizers ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$)
- 539 CFP_f Gate price of industrial fertilizers ($\text{€}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
- 540 CP_c Crop price ($\text{€}\cdot\text{metric ton}^{-1}$)
- 541 Df_m Distance from the industrial fertilizer plant to the fields (km)
- 542 $Dp_{m,p}$ Distance from the fertilizer production sites to the fields (km)
- 543 $FP_{p,r}$ Gate price of fertilizers ($\text{€}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
- 544 $IFP_{c,p}$ Average gate price of the industrial fertilizers required to fertilize each crop ($\text{€}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
- 545 lc Labor costs ($\text{€}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$)
- 546 $M_{c,m}$ Matrix of large parameters
- 547 $M_{c,m,p}, M_{c,m,p,s}$ Tensors of large parameters
- 548 $O_{c,m,p,s}$ Tensor of zeros and ones indicating the possible combinations of c, m, p and s
- 549 $P_{c,p,s}$ Amount of fertilizers required to fertilize 1 ha ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$)
- 550 sc Spreading costs ($\text{€}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)
- 551 tc Transportation costs ($\text{€}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$)
- 552 $TCFC_{c,m,p,s}$ Total costs related to the purchase, transportation and spreading of the industrial
553 fertilizers required to complement the fertilization of 1 ha with organic fertilizers ($\text{€}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$)
- 554 $Vfert_{p,s}$ Matrix of ones and zeros indicating the selection of industrial fertilizers
- 555 $Vind_p$ Vector of ones and zeros indicating the selection of the industrial fertilizers

556 $Vorg_p$ Vector of ones and zeros indicating the selection of the organic fertilizers

557 w_c Water requirements ($m^3 \cdot ha^{-1}$)

558 wc Water costs ($€ \cdot m^{-3}$)

559 $Yield_{c,p,s}$ Crop yield ($metric\ ton \cdot ha^{-1}$)

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562 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

563 Model parameters, DNDC, LCA and Life Cycle Costing results.

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797 **SYNOPSIS**

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799 A multi-objective optimization framework integrating life cycle and Stackelberg models was
800 developed to design sustainable circular waste management systems